

International Journal of Education & Applied Sciences Research (IJEASR)

ISSN: 2349 –2899 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –4808 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/getCurrentIssue/157>

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INDIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM AND ITS CORRELATION WITH TEACHING AND CLASSROOM AUTHENTICITY OF PRESENT MODERN SCENARIO

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Abstract

This paper is highly concern and mark approach to give a clear picture of Indian education system and ensures for a number of measures to bring advanced update in the system of Indian education. As we know, India is not remarkable not only for its logical, classical and research oriented theoretical experiment in the field of education but also for its world wide popularity. When we talk about the concept of teaching its deep attachment with a word “Psychology “comes in our mind. As its often said” A good psychology and psychological observation of teacher can introduce him a real guide, mentor, and a good companion for his/her students. In India the concept of education actually starts from the grass-root of “ Teaching concept of a teacher” historically India is a country where the concept of education which observes as the normal and abnormal, the ordinary and extraordinary, illusion and reality, resignation and desire rub shoulders to find a way to select a path of bright and esteemed world of “career”.

Key words: Role of Educational Psychology, psychological observation, grass-root,

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Reference this paper as: Kapil Dev Sharma, (2014). “Indian Education system and its correlation with teaching and classroom authenticity of present modern scenario,” *International Journal of Education & Applied Sciences Research, Vol.1, Issue 1, May-2014, pp 27-32*

Introduction

A highly qualified teacher, having a number of honourable degree from a prestigious university, was surprised to find a negative feedback given by students, starts his personal observation and during this exercise he was much serious to make his personal interaction with a group of student, check his teaching theories and level stability with student, reminded his previous lecture delivered in class-room. Finally evolved to write a note of classroom disturbance related to infrastructure, suddenly he stopped near a student desk, started to give his keen look upon the

surface of desk mentioned “We need change”. The word change finally makes him aware to found the meaning and definition of change in himself. Teaching is actually a series of interaction between the learner and the teacher with the explicit goal of changing the behaviour of the learner. On other hand we can say teaching has undergone a number of changes during the last few years. Till recently teaching was equated with telling. The knowledge aspect of teaching was considered most important, in the old approach to teaching mainly “An imparting knowledge and skill” the emphasis was on the content what is to be taught, however both these approaches are teacher- centered and the subject matter is forced upon the learners. Somewhere “Teaching in a process of interaction between the teacher and the taught”. In a new definition “Teaching is something that facilitates others to learn”.

Teaching in the process of research

Early research in the area of teaching suffered from many defects such as failure to observe the various aspects of the teaching activities, lack of theoretical framework, inadequate criteria to determine teaching effectiveness and lack of concern for contextual effect. The new research activity, however is directed towards the observation of actual instances of instruction in the classroom, since the publication of “Pygmalion in the classroom” researchers are trying to identify two factors given below.

- 1- What is that the teacher actually does during instruction in the classroom and how does it lead to change in the attitude of students?
- 2- What response is produced upon the performance of students by the expectations expressed by the teacher?

In the major theories of teaching around five specialized have been identified.

- 1- Communication- Word communication are usually investigated into two categories Verbal communication and Non-verbal communication both communication have their different properties still both way of communication are highly responsible to full fill the objectives of communication.
- 2- Teacher's personality- Teacher is not only a concept of teaching but also plays a role of guide, mentor, and companion. So the personality of teacher affects the process and even result of teaching.
- 3- Role theory and its objectives- Research in this area attempts to throw light on how the teacher perceives her/ his role how it effects the attainment and behaviour of their students. This theory is helping to bring about the necessary changes in the curricula and evolving new methods of instruction and approach to the teaching process. It also tackle the day to day problems and develops an appropriate verbal and non- verbal patterns of communication
- 4- Management of learning- The process of teaching and learning is always a part of discussion. Research in this area helps the teachers to solve the problem of discipline in the class room and to

mention an atmosphere appropriate to learning.

- 5- Taxonomy of educational objectives- The classification of educational objectives has compelled us to think why we teach whatever we teach in the classroom. It helps the teacher to specify the instructional objectives and also to find out whatever those objectives have been achieved.

The next stage of research invite us in a room, full with wooden furniture , A black board which bottom show a straight line of a particular dust of chalk, called classroom. A number of study forcefully to say classroom as a group. A five year old child enrolled in the first standard of a school by his/ her parents. The choice of the school is made by the parents. The choice of the school for child has made by the parents of child. In which the division of the first standard is the child going to sit? This is decided by the administrator of the school. The child himself has no choice in this regard and he suddenly found himself in a group. The teacher talks to him not as individual but as a member of the class group. She tells a story to the whole class and not to an individual child. She addresses her question to the whole class although only one of them may answer at a time, before joining the school the child was the center of attention of all member at home, this does not happen now in the school. He has to play a new role what is that role. The teacher directs the activity in the class as a group activity. The students sit together listen to work with the same researcher, read common text books, and have common task and common although they do not learn at the same level or speed. They play together, watch a film through all these activities the child tries to become a member of the class group wants to belong to nit. As the in interaction and

feeling of relationship develops, he feels more and more comfortable. As years pass he accepts the role as a member of a particular class..... In whatever way the children are grouped into various classes, the grouping is not choked by the children. They come to the class because they have to. They differ in their temperament and hobbies and from different socio-economical background. Each child tries to develop their feelings of belongingness by relating to other members. The need it relates the other people in universal. No one likes to remain a stranger or be isolated because being isolated gives a feeling of insignificance, inadequacy and emptiness'. It causes anxiety. It is a duty of a teacher not only to help students but also motivate them to touch the peak of success.

Effective teaching and the concept of teacher effectiveness

If we discuss about the profession of "Teaching" it is rather a challenging, complex, experienced based and rewarding profession. Now teaching has come to be seen as science. According to Sinner "Teacher is a specialist in human behaviour, whose assignment is to bring about extraordinary complex change in extra ordinary complex material. A teacher proves to be effective to the extant he or she is able to use the exciting competence for the achievement of the expected results. Recent research studies focus on the teacher behaviour in and out of the classroom to define teacher effectiveness. The science of human behaviour works on the problem of learning and teaching and discuss various approaches to the effective teaching. These definitions are in four important categories.

- 1- Appropriate practice
- 2- Motivational fact
- 3- Developmental awareness
- 4- Task description
- 5- Purpose
- 6- Knowledge of result
- 7- Individual differentiation

Characteristic of a teacher fostering interaction

When we talk about the personality of a teacher his behaviour is always focused, now what is behaviour of a teacher whose class is active and alive with a continues give and take between all the members including the teacher and yet a good amount of learning takes place in it, without the children turning rowdy? Psychology of a teacher included thinking, planning, questioning, and decision making by teacher. It is obvious thought process of a teacher behaviour hence studding various angle of the thought process will prove to b useful to educational theorists, teacher educators, curriculum designers, researchers, policy makers, and school administrators and also to teacher. It should be remembered that teachers thinking during the classroom interaction is totally different from what they do before and after classroom interaction. Now how can a teacher as certain whatever there id healthy interaction in hr/ his classroom? According to the Flanders technique of “interaction analysis” helps a teacher to gt an idea about it. It is an observations procedure where in the verbal behaviour of the teacher is classified into seven categories of “Silence and confusion” is added to denote the intervals, where neither the student nor the teacher is making any verbal responses. We should remember that interaction and cohesiveness are interdependent, if the class group is cohesive, there will be more interaction and more interaction will bring about more

cohesiveness, which build the morals of the class. In order to develop their positive feelings, showing belief in the child, listening to him attentively, accepting his ideas, helping the child to gain competence, being patient with him and such other activity. Similarly giving support to chose who lack confidence, helping them to locate answers, giving chance to elaborate ideas and relate own experience. On other hand seeking for the children opinion and experience, giving him opportunities, to use many media of communication, providing plenty of books and other materials, affording opportunity for the child to compare his new experience with the previous ones and draw inference and generalization also making the child aware of the positive side of his personality and so on , somewhere it may never be fulfilled the objectives of teaching, if a teacher not make him to evaluate with discrimination and providing similar social activities for growth.

Conclusion

The present scenario is full with a number of changing situations, where particularly activity to bring out the desired change of behaviour and attitude by the use of old lecture deliverance theory or classical demonstration method. Today to maintain appropriate classroom dynamics, new methods of teaching have to be used. The teacher has to be sensitive to the response o each student. A teacher must develop the nature and habit of observation. He / She must aware of all changes that take place in the classroom and can immediately control them. A dynamic teacher will spot children in need and those with family habit to cultivate efficient study habit among students. Similarly a need of democratic discipline is required; giving punishment liberally in the name of toughness and realism is detrimental to classroom dynamics. It should way to democratic discipline. Punishment should

not be out of proportion with the offence and should be administered impersonally and not out of hatred for the offender. The student should feel that punishing him is not a pleasure for the teacher; In fact it hurts the teacher more than the child himself. When we think about the problem solving experience. A discussion can be held to find out the possible solutions. This is an excellent way of having a glimpse of the Child's world, their behaviour, and their relations with friends etc. This method is now successful in changing attitude in the desired directions then the traditional teaching concept. Teacher can easily correct misapprehension and misunderstanding review important aspects and provide a broader and more complete picture. Teacher does not have high expectation from the students of lower socio – economical backgrounds. Their neglect of these students engender in them highly changed negative attitudes towards learning. The teacher is mostly responsible for the emotional climate of the classroom. A friendly, pleasant and enthusiastic teacher creates an enthusiastic atmosphere. It is a pattern of behaviour which student learn from their elders and is fostered by misunderstanding and frustration. It is believed of some people that teaching is a creative, dynamic but

intuitive activity and only a born teacher can feel the right moment to encourage her/ his student in a precisely right activity to ensure their progress.

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